

Enhancing the Mechanical and Durability Properties of Burnt Clay Bricks Using Waste Glass Powder

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ABSTRACT:

The increased demand for construction materials and environmental hazards due to industrial-associated wastes provide scope for sustainable solution pathways. Hence, this study focused on determining the possibility of using waste glass powder as a replacement for clay in burnt clay bricks for improved mechanical performance and durability. According to the tests performed under ASTM, the bricks were executed for compressive strength, modulus of rupture, water absorption, apparent porosity, efflorescence resistance, and ultrasonic pulse velocity for various WGP substitutions starting from 0% and ending with 25%. The results of the tests indicated that samples with up to 20% recorded the highest increase in compressive strength and modulus of rupture of approximately 25% and 41%, respectively. Excellent results proved that WGP improved structure integrity and durability, enhancing their potential as a waste management solution as an eco-friendly additive that reduces dependence on natural clay. This study concluded that the WGP-modified bricks can be a valid replacement for sustainable construction applications. To enhance the suitability of WGP for sustainable construction, more studies must be carried out on optimizing firing parameters, long-term durability evaluation, and scaling up production processes to facilitate broader industrial adoption.

Keywords: Waste Glass Powder (WGP), Burnt Clay Bricks, Sustainable Construction, Mechanical Properties, Durability Enhancement.

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INTRODUCTION

In many parts of the world, including Pakistan, bricks are a customary building material used for walls, load-bearing structures, pavements, etc. Historically made from clay, bricks are appreciated for their strength, low cost, and abundance. "The intense extraction and removal of topsoil for the production of bricks have resulted in serious environmental degradation and resource depletion. [1].

Most worrying is this trend, especially in agricultural regions wherein topsoil is crucially needed to maintain food production. Conventional brick manufacturing techniques involve kiln firing with high energy consumption, greatly contributing to greenhouse gas emissions and environmental pollution. [2].

Meanwhile, industrial waste has now become a global concern in many ways. Among various types of waste, WGP, as the byproduct of the production line of the glass industry, plays a key role. Only in Pakistan tremendous quantities of glass waste are generated, which enhances the problem of finding an efficient route for its management [3]Pakistan's ever-growing manufacturing sector generates a large amount of glass waste every year. Improper disposal worsens landfill shortages and contributes to environmental pollution. However, WGP contains a high silica content, providing a promising opportunity for recycling and utilization in constructing materials. [4].

The application of WGP in manufacturing bricks has already been shown to be a viable alternative to fired clay bricks from a sustainable and technologically feasible perspective. Silica, an essential constituent, provides strength, hardness, and resistance to abrasion for bricks, especially under diverse environmental conditions. Several studies reported that the compressive strength of the clay bricks was increased considerably upon the addition of WGP, while water absorption was reduced and resistance to efflorescence improved. These modified bricks not only meet but often surpass the performance of conventional bricks, adhering to international standards for mechanical properties and durability. [5], [6]. Furthermore, integrating WGP into brick production supports the principles of a circular economy by converting industrial waste into a valuable resource. [7].

WGP could be utilized as an ideal additive to burnt clay bricks because the pursuit would resolve two major challenges at a global scale, one about environmental degradation and the other concerning industrial waste management. To this end, several bricks were prepared to incorporate varying WGP dosages; several of its major properties—mechanical and durability—are assessed herein. Properties studied on bricks containing 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25% WGP. As per ASTM standards, bricks were fabricated and analyzed for their mechanical and durability aspects. The most crucial parameters investigated are compressive strength, flexural strength, water absorption, porosity, and efflorescence resistance [8].

This paper investigates the environmental and economic viability of bricks modified with WGP to develop sustainable construction materials. The results are expected to offer a practical solution by reducing the demand for natural clays, overcoming industrial residue problems, and contributing to eco-friendly construction.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Materials

Clay

The main raw material used for brick manufacturing, clay, was supplied from a source in Quetta. The chemical composition test showed a high percentage of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 , which are responsible for the strength, plasticity, and durability of the bricks. The oversize clay was passed through a sieve to achieve a uniform particle size and then dried to remove excess moisture before manufacturing.

Figure 1. XRD Pattern of Soil/Clay

Waste Glass Powder (WGP):

Waste Glass Powder was obtained from industrial waste in Lahore, Pakistan. Waste glass was ground using a ball mill to achieve a fine particle size of less than 150 μm . Chemical analysis showed that the silica content is high, and the amorphous structure of WGP supports its pozzolanic reactivity. Due to this property, WGP has the potential to enhance the strength and durability of bricks when used as a partial replacement for clay.

Figure 2. XRD Pattern of Waste Glass Powder (WGP)

Table 1. Properties of Clay and WGP

	Clay	WGP
SiO ₂	57.05	61.85
TiO ₂	0.68	0.04
Al ₂ O ₃	11.91	1.37
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.96	0
MnO	0.08	0
MgO	2.52	2.99
CaO	8.98	4.17
Na ₂ O	1.86	5.27
K ₂ O	2.21	0.06
P ₂ O ₅	0.14	0
LOI	9.59	24.3

Water

Clean, potable water was used during the mixing process to ensure uniform consistency and proper hydration of the clay and WGP mixture.

Figure 3. Clay and WGP

Mix Proportions

Six different proportions of clay and WGP were prepared for the study. The proportions are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Mix Proportions of Clay and WGP

Sample Code	Clay Content (% by Weight)	WGP Content (% by Weight)
M0 (Control)	100	0
M1	95	5
M2	90	10
M3	85	15
M4	80	20
M5	75	25

Methodology

Preparation of Materials

- Clay: The clay was dried to eliminate moisture and sieved to achieve a uniform particle size, ensuring consistency during mixing.
- Waste Glass Powder (WGP): Glass waste was processed using a ball mill to produce a fine powder with a particle size of less than 150 μm . This preparation ensured optimal mixing and enhanced pozzolanic activity during the firing process.

Mixing

The clay and WGP were accurately weighed and mixed according to the proportions specified in Table 1. A mechanical mixer was employed to ensure a uniform blend, while the water content was carefully regulated to achieve the appropriate consistency for molding.

Molding

The prepared mixture was poured into standard molds (230 mm \times 114 mm \times 76 mm) and manually compacted to minimize voids and improve density.

Drying

The molded bricks were air-dried for 48 hours to eliminate surface moisture. Subsequently, they were oven-dried at 105°C for 24 hours to ensure complete moisture removal.

Firing

The dried bricks were fired in a commercial kiln at temperatures ranging from 800°C to 1000°C. The firing process was conducted in three stages:

- Initial Heating: A gradual increase in temperature to eliminate any remaining residual moisture.
- Sintering: Maintaining the peak temperature for 6 hours to achieve the desired material properties.
- Cooling: Gradual cooling to avoid cracking or thermal shock.

Figure 4. Mixing, Clay Balls, Brick Casting, and Kiln

Testing Procedures

ASTM standards tested the bricks to assess their mechanical and durability properties.

Mechanical Tests

- Compressive Strength: The load-bearing capacity of the bricks was measured using a universal testing machine.
- Modulus of Rupture: The flexural strength and resistance to cracking were evaluated.

Figure 5: Compressive Strength and Modulus of Rupture Test

Durability Tests

- Water Absorption: The porosity and durability of the bricks were assessed.
- Apparent Porosity: The void spaces within the bricks were evaluated to quantify porosity.
- Efflorescence Resistance: This test was conducted to determine the tendency of salt deposition on the brick surface when exposed to moisture.
- Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (UPV): The internal integrity and density of the bricks were measured [9]

Figure 6. Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (UPV) and Apparent Porosity

Data Analysis

Each test was performed on all six samples (0% to 25% WGP content) with three replicates for each proportion to ensure accuracy. The results were statistically analyzed to identify performance trends and determine the optimal WGP proportion for improved brick properties.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Weight per Unit Area

Adding WGP increased the weight per unit area of the bricks, which the higher density of WGP can explain compared with clay. Fine WGP particles fill the voids within the clay matrix and increase the overall mass. Table 3 highlights the progressive increase in weight per unit area with higher proportions of WGP.

The control brick (0% WGP) exhibited a weight per unit area of 98.50 kg/m², which increased to 117.43 kg/m² for the 25% WGP sample. This linear trend demonstrates a proportional relationship between the WGP content and the weight per unit area. These findings are consistent with previous studies, which have reported that the high specific gravity of WGP significantly contributes to the densification of bricks. [1], [10]. An increased weight per unit area indicates enhanced compactness and structural stability, critical properties for construction materials.

Table 3. Weight per Unit Area of Bricks

Specimen	Weight (kg)	Area (m ²)	Weight per Unit Area (kg/m ²)
C (0% WGP)	2.571	0.0261	98.5
G5 (5% WGP)	2.924	0.0261	112.03
G10 (10% WGP)	2.97	0.0261	113.79
G15 (15% WGP)	2.975	0.0261	113.98
G20 (20% WGP)	3.029	0.0261	116.05
G25 (25% WGP)	3.065	0.0261	117.43

Water Absorption

Water absorption is a crucial parameter for evaluating the durability and porosity of bricks. The incorporation of WGP significantly reduced water absorption in the samples. The control sample (0% WGP) had a water absorption rate of 21.23%, which decreased to 18.49% for the 25% WGP sample, as illustrated in Table 4. This may be explained by fine WGP particles filling the voids in the clay matrix, reducing porosity and limiting water absorption. The reduced water absorption, therefore, improves the durability of bricks by enhancing their resistance to environmental degradation and freeze-thaw cycles. These results are similar to those reported by Ali et al.[10], who observed a

26.14% reduction in water absorption with a 20% addition of WGP. Similarly, Tripathi and Chauhan[1] Reported a decrease in water absorption to 8.5% with a 20% replacement of WGP. These findings further validate the potential of WGP-modified bricks as a superior alternative to conventional clay bricks, particularly for applications requiring enhanced water resistance.

Table 4. Water Absorption of Bricks

Specimen	Initial Weight (kg)	Final Weight (kg)	Water Absorption (%)
C (0% WGP)	2.571	3.117	21.23
G5 (5% WGP)	2.924	3.528	20.65
G10 (10% WGP)	2.97	3.549	19.49
G15 (15% WGP)	2.975	3.551	19.36
G20 (20% WGP)	3.029	3.612	19.24
G25 (25% WGP)	3.065	3.632	18.49

Apparent Porosity

Apparent porosity is one of the major factors that may affect the durability and structure of bricks. This research article focuses on apparent porosity in bricks made from blends with various proportions of waste glass powder to replace clay. The results in Table 5 revealed a consistent decrease in apparent porosity with increasing WGP content.

The control bricks (0% WGP) exhibited the highest apparent porosity at 48.70%. As the proportion of WGP increased, the porosity decreased progressively, reaching 39.12% for bricks with 25% WGP replacement. This reduction in porosity can be attributed to the fine particles of WGP filling the voids within the clay matrix, resulting in denser and less porous bricks. Similar findings have been documented in the literature, where the incorporation of WGP reduced pore volume and surface area due to enhanced densification during the firing process. [6], [11].

The reduced porosity observed in WGP-modified bricks provides several advantages, including improved water resistance and enhanced mechanical strength—lower porosity limits water ingress, reducing the risk of frost damage and efflorescence. Moreover, denser bricks exhibit superior load-bearing capacity and greater durability under environmental stresses. These findings are consistent with previous studies, which demonstrate that incorporating WGP significantly decreases open porosity, enhancing the fired bricks' performance.[10], [12].

Table 5. Apparent Porosity of Bricks with Different WGP Proportions

Specimen	Dry Weight (D) (gm)	Suspended Weight (S) (gm)	Saturated Weight (W) (gm)	Volume (V) (cm ³)	Apparent Porosity (P%)
C (0% WGP)	0.414	0.256	0.564	0.308	48.7
G5 (5% WGP)	0.482	0.302	0.64	0.338	46.75
G10 (10% WGP)	0.632	0.394	0.83	0.436	45.41
G15 (15% WGP)	0.492	0.306	0.644	0.338	44.97
G20 (20% WGP)	0.718	0.438	0.932	0.494	43.32
G25 (25% WGP)	0.607	0.372	0.758	0.386	39.12

The relationship between Waste Glass Powder (WGP) content and brick properties is reflected in apparent porosity and water absorption trends. As the proportion of WGP increases, both parameters show a significant reduction. Apparent porosity decreases from 48.7% in the control specimen (0% WGP) to 39.12% in bricks containing 25% WGP. This trend is clearly in line with the reduction in porosity, as fewer voids allow the brick to absorb less water. It was established that this property is improved by including WGP in the brick composition, leading to enhanced durability and better resistance against moisture-related degradation. The observed improvements validate the effectiveness of WGP as a sustainable and practical additive for brick manufacturing.

Figure 6. Comparison of Apparent Porosity and Water Absorption

Efflorescence

Efflorescence, a durability issue resulting from the migration of soluble salts to the brick surface, was evaluated in brick specimens incorporating Waste Glass Powder (WGP). The control specimens (0% WGP) exhibited slight efflorescence, affecting approximately 7% of the surface area after seven days. This phenomenon was attributed to the clay's high calcium oxide (CaO) content, which was measured at approximately 9%. In contrast, including WGP, which contains a significantly lower calcium oxide (CaO) content (4.17%), resulted in a progressive reduction in efflorescence. Bricks with 25% WGP exhibited minimal efflorescence, affecting only 4% of the surface area.

Figure 7. Affected Area (%)

This improvement is attributed to the reduced presence of efflorescence-inducing compounds, such as calcium oxide (CaO) and ferric oxide (Fe_2O_3), in WGP-modified bricks. While the clay contained ferric oxide at 5%, which is within recommended limits, WGP lacked Fe_2O_3 entirely, further contributing to the reduction of efflorescence in the modified specimens. These findings align with studies highlighting the importance of reduced salt migration in improving the aesthetics and durability of bricks. [7], [13].

The reduction in efflorescence across the samples underscores the effectiveness of WGP in enhancing brick quality. The average affected surface area decreased from 10.73 in² (7%) in the control specimens to 7.09 in² (4%) in bricks containing 25% WGP. These results demonstrate that incorporating WGP effectively mitigates efflorescence, enhancing masonry structures' aesthetic appeal and longevity.

Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity Test

The UPV test method is a non-destructive test for material quality. [9]. The results from UPV tests on brick specimens with Waste Glass Powder additions showed a consistent improvement in UPV values, ranging from 1.45 mm/μs for the control specimen (0% WGP) to 1.95 mm/μs for bricks with 25% WGP. This trend correlates with improvements in compressive strength and microstructural densification achieved through WGP incorporation.

Table 6. Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (UPV)

Specimen	Length (mm)	Time (micro sec)	Velocity (mm/micro sec)	Average Ultrasonic Pulse Velocity (mm/micro sec)
C	228.6	152.21	1.5	1.45
		169	1.35	
		152	1.5	
G5	228.6	142.2	1.6	1.61
		133.5	1.71	
		148.5	1.53	
G10	228.6	132	1.73	1.75
		133.56	1.71	
		125	1.82	
G15	228.6	124	1.84	1.86
		122	1.87	
		121	1.88	
G20	228.6	112.8	2.02	1.87
		110	2.07	
		149	1.53	
G25	228.6	122.5	1.86	1.95
		125.6	1.82	
		104	2.19	

The increase in UPV values is attributed to the reduction in voids and improved homogeneity within the brick matrix, driven by the pozzolanic activity of WGP. WGP fills microstructural voids and chemically reacts to form secondary bonding phases, which reduce discontinuities and enable ultrasonic waves to propagate more efficiently through the material. This enhancement in velocity reflects improved material quality, aligning with the findings of Koroth et al. [14], who observed a positive correlation between UPV values and brick durability.

UPV values for all specimens fell within the durable range of 1–3.5 mm/μs, as recommended by ASTM standards. However, none of the specimens exceeded the 3.5 mm/μs upper durability threshold. The control specimen exhibited the lowest velocity, while bricks with 25% WGP achieved the highest values, further confirming that incorporating WGP improves the structural integrity of bricks.

The UPV test results also strongly correlated with compressive strength evaluations, with both methods exhibiting consistent trends. This alignment reinforces the reliability of UPV as a rapid and cost-effective tool for assessing the quality of WGP-modified bricks.

Compressive Strength

Compressive strength is the most important property of a brick when resisting structural loads. In this study, bricks were made with varying percentages of WGP as a partial replacement for clay, and the results showed a significant improvement in strength compared to the control sample (0% WGP).

Incorporating WGP enhanced compressive strength due to its densifying effect and pozzolanic reactivity, which improved the microstructure and bonding characteristics of the material.

The control bricks exhibited a compressive strength of 28 MPa. Replacing 20% of the clay with WGP significantly increased compressive strength, reaching 35 MPa—an improvement of approximately 25% (see Figure 4). This optimal performance is attributed to the ability of WGP to fill voids within the clay matrix and to form additional binding phases during the firing process. The formation of a glassy phase at high temperatures promotes densification, further enhancing the material's load-bearing capacity. These findings are supported by previous studies, which have shown that WGP improves the mechanical properties of bricks by reducing porosity and achieving better particle packing. [6], [15].

Figure 8. Compressive Strength in Different WGP %

Interestingly, the compressive strength decreased slightly at higher replacement levels (above 20%). For example, bricks with 25% WGP exhibited a compressive strength of 34 MPa. This reduction can be attributed to the excessive replacement of clay, which disrupts the structural integrity of the matrix and reduces the availability of sufficient clay to form a robust ceramic phase during the firing process. Similar observations were reported by Adediran et al. [13], who found that the optimum WGP content in bricks balances enhanced strength and structural cohesion.

These results also underscore the environmental benefits of incorporating WGP. By decreasing the need for virgin clay, WGP helps conserve natural resources while offering a sustainable solution for managing industrial glass waste. Additionally, the firing temperature for WGP-modified bricks is lower, ranging between 800–900°C, compared to the higher temperature of 1000°C required for traditional clay bricks. This reduction in firing temperature contributes to energy savings and lower carbon emissions during production [1].

The combination of enhanced mechanical strength and environmental sustainability positions WGP-modified bricks as a compelling alternative to conventional clay bricks. These findings indicate that a 20% WGP replacement is optimal for superior performance, making the material suitable for structural and non-structural applications in the construction industry.

Modulus of Rupture

The modulus of rupture (MOR), a key indicator of flexural strength, showed significant improvements with the addition of Waste Glass Powder (WGP) as a partial replacement for clay. The control bricks (0% WGP) demonstrated a MOR of 2.20 MPa, which increased progressively with higher WGP content, reaching a peak of 3.10 MPa for bricks containing 25% WGP. The observed 41% improvement in MOR underscores the role of WGP in enhancing the tensile resistance of the brick matrix. Similar trends have been documented by Rahmouni et al. [16] Who reported that WGP

improved the flexural strength of alkali-activated mortars due to its pozzolanic reactivity and enhanced microstructural properties.

Figure 9. Modulus of Rupture

The enhancement in MOR can be attributed to the micro-aggregate filling effect of WGP, which minimizes voids and increases matrix density during the firing process. This densification, combined with the formation of strong binding phases such as calcium silicate hydrates, improves load distribution within the bricks [17]. Microstructural analyses confirm that WGP-modified bricks exhibit reduced porosity and improved interfacial bonding, contributing to their superior mechanical performance.

The results also comply with ASTM C597 standards for structural clay bricks. [18], which specifies a minimum MOR of 0.65 MPa. This study's significantly higher MOR values underscore the potential of WGP-modified bricks for structural applications. Furthermore, as noted by Zhang and Yue [2], the thermal stability and enhanced durability of WGP-modified bricks make them suitable for environments subject to mechanical and thermal stresses.

However, optimizing WGP content is crucial, as excessive replacement may lead to brittleness or degradation of mechanical properties. Future research could focus on optimizing firing temperatures and exploring the long-term durability of WGP-modified bricks under various environmental conditions.

CONCLUSION

This study successfully demonstrated the feasibility of utilizing Waste Glass Powder (WGP) to replace clay in producing burnt clay bricks partially. The experimental results showed that incorporating WGP significantly enhances bricks' mechanical and durability properties. Key findings include improved compressive strength, increased modulus of rupture, reduced water absorption, lower apparent porosity, and enhanced resistance to efflorescence. Additionally, the ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) results highlighted the structural integrity of WGP-modified bricks. These outcomes validate the potential of WGP as a sustainable additive that reduces reliance on natural clay and provides an eco-friendly solution for managing industrial glass waste. The optimal replacement level of 20% WGP was identified, balancing strength, durability, and material compatibility.

FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

- Further research should focus on the impact of firing temperature and duration on the mechanical and durability properties of WGP-modified bricks, aiming to optimize energy efficiency and improve performance.
- To assess the long-term performance of WGP-modified bricks, long-term durability tests under varying environmental conditions, such as freeze-thaw cycles, should be conducted.
- To facilitate commercial adoption, explore the scalability of WGP-modified brick production, including cost-benefit analysis.
- Employ advanced techniques like scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) to gain deeper insights into the microstructural changes induced by WGP.
- Investigate the combined effects of WGP and other industrial by-products, such as fly ash or slag, to develop multi-component sustainable construction materials.
- Research on performance of WGP-modified bricks under real masonry applications and determine their suitability for a broad range of construction uses, including both load-bearing and non-load-bearing applications

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